

Identification of thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines in rice germplasm

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Seventy traditional rice germplasm lines were collected from hilly areas of Koraput, Phulbani, and Mayurbhanj districts of Orissa (eastern India) where the temperature at panicle initiation (PI) stage is below 31°C. These lines, grown at the National Bureau of Plant Genetic Resources Base Center, Cuttack, during the wet season (WS) (Jun-Sep 1991) where day/night temperature is 32-24°C at PI, showed 60-100% spikelet sterility. In the dry season (DS) (Dec-Mar 1992) they showed normal fertility (30/14°C at PI). These lines, along with Yelik Meedon (IRGC 33888), a variety from Myanmar, were tested at IRRI during 1994 WS for pollen fertility. Four lines did not germinate, but some of the other 67 did (Table 1): 17 lines were fully fertile, 11 fertile, 19 partially fertile, 14 partially sterile, 5 sterile, and only Yelik Meedon completely sterile. Two plants of Navakathi were completely sterile, whereas overall sterility varied from 92 to 100%. The PI stage occurred in late August (32/24°C, based on IRRI data). Two plants of Navakathi (STM11-1 and STM11-19)

and Yelik Meedon were ratooned in pots in a greenhouse and in a phytotron. They were retested in 1995 DS in the greenhouse where day/night temperatures varied from 29-21°C on 11 Feb to 34-24°C on 25 Apr when PI took place in these lines in the phytotron at 27-21°C. During 1995 DS, these three lines showed variable fertility (Table 2).

Navakathi (STM11-1 and STM11-19) showed complete pollen sterility (100%) at temperatures higher than 31°C and Yelik Meedon at higher than 30°C at PI (18 d before flowering) but all showed fertile pollen at lower temperatures in the net house and phytotron. Thus, they behaved as thermosensitive genic male sterile (TGMS) lines.

These putative TGMS lines were crossed with IR64 and IR36. The F₁s had fertile pollen (60-80%), indicating that TGMS in these lines is under recessive

Table 1. Rice germplasm lines in different fertility classes. IRRI, 1994 DS.

Pollen fertility	Fertility class	Lines (no.)
81-100	Fully fertile	17
61-80	Fertile	11
31-60	Partially fertile	19
11-30	Partially sterile	14
1-10	Sterile	5
0	Completely sterile	1

gene control. An F₂ population of STM11-1 and IR64 was grown during 1995 DS at IRRI. The plants reached PI stage during the first week of April when the day/night temperatures ranged from 32 to 24°C. Among the 250 plants scored for spikelet fertility, 189 were fertile and 61 were completely sterile, giving a good fit to the ratio of 3:1 ($\chi^2 = 0.084$, $P = 0.80-0.70$). Thus the study confirmed that the TGMS trait of Navakathi is controlled by a single recessive gene. ■

Table 2. Pollen fertility (%) at different temperatures. IRRI, 1995 DS.

Designation	Variety	Temperature (°C) at PI stage (18 d before flowering)						
		27-21	29-21	30-21	31-22	32-23	33-23	34-24
STM11-1	Navakathi	80	80	70	10	0	-	0
STM11-19	Navakathi	80	80	75	15	0	0	0
IRGC33888	Yelik Meedon	85	80	5	0	0	0	-
	IR36	82	-	-	-	80	-	-
	IR64	85	-	-	-	82	-	-
(STM11-1/IR64)F ₁		-	-	-	-	60	-	-
(STM11-19/IR36)F ₁		-	-	-	-	78	-	-
(IRGC33888/IR64)F ₁		-	-	-	-	80	-	-

Floral traits influencing outcrossing rate in rice

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Commercial seed production highly depends on the extent of outcrossing, which depends on floral characters, anthesis, anther dehiscence, and a number of environmental factors. We evaluated the amount of natural outcrossing and its relation to floral traits.

The parental lines of 20 hybrids in-

volving the four cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines V20A(L1), Zs97A(L2), IR58025 A(L3), and IR62829 A(L4) and five effective restorers IR24 (T1), IR54742-22-19-3 (T2), IR29723-143-3-2-1 (T3), IR9761-19-1 (T4), and ARC11353 (T5) were raised in a randomized block design with two replications during 1993 kharif season (Jul-Sep). A row ratio of 4:2 was adopted. Three rows of a pollen barrier, Purple Puttu, were raised around the crossing block and between each cross combination. Ten plants for both A and R lines were maintained in each row and seeds were collected from individual crosses. Ten

plants in each of four CMS lines and five restorers in each replication were selected randomly for observations of filament length (FL), anther length (AL), anther breadth (AB), and pollen diameter (PD) in restorer lines and style length (SYL), stigma length (SGL), ovary length (OL), and ovary breadth (OB) using a standard ocular micrometer. For observation of stigma exertion, 100 spikelets that had already opened and closed were selected from each plant. Those in which the stigmas were seen outside were counted and expressed as percentages. Simple correlation coefficients were estimated.

IR58025 A showed the highest mean outcrossing rate, 16.67% (see table). Individual combinations with high outcrossings were IR58025 A/ IR29723-143-3-2-1, IR58025 A/ IR24, and V20 A/ IR29723-143-3-2-1. Maximum anther

length and breadth were found in IR54742-22-19-3. High filament length and pollen diameter was recorded for IR29723-143-3-2-1; V20 A showed lengthy stigma; and IR58025 A had high stigma exertion and ovary

breadth. Except for stigma exertion, none of the varieties were linked closely with outcrossing rate. The lines IR58025 A, IR29723-143-3-2-1, and IR54742-22-19-3 can be well utilized for hybrid rice improvement. ■

Outcrossing rate in some hybrid varieties and its relationship with floral traits. Tamil Nadu, India.

Cross ^a	Filament length (mm)	Anther length (mm)	Anther breadth (mm)	Pollen diameter (mm)	Style length (mm)	Stigma length (mm)	Ovary length (mm)	Ovary breadth (mm)	SE (%)	Outcrossing rate (%)
L1/T1	1.67	2.06	0.57	0.036	1.13	1.45	0.50	0.38	35.65	18.18
L1/T2	2.32	2.70	0.76	0.038	1.13	1.45	0.50	0.38	35.65	13.13
L1/T3	2.84	1.75	0.55	0.054	1.13	1.45	0.50	0.38	35.65	18.91
L1/T4	2.25	1.66	0.61	0.035	1.13	1.45	0.50	0.38	35.65	15.90
L1/T5	1.63	1.81	0.63	0.040	1.13	1.45	0.50	0.38	35.65	15.74
Mean										16.37
L2/T1	1.67	2.06	0.57	0.036	1.44	1.07	0.58	0.52	32.00	12.21
L2/T2	2.32	2.70	0.76	0.038	1.44	1.07	0.58	0.52	32.00	16.09
L2/T3	2.84	1.75	0.55	0.054	1.44	1.07	0.58	0.52	32.00	18.29
L2/T4	2.25	1.66	0.61	0.035	1.44	1.07	0.58	0.52	32.00	10.41
L2/T5	1.63	1.81	0.63	0.040	1.44	1.07	0.58	0.52	32.00	9.53
Mean										13.31
L3/T1	1.67	2.06	0.57	0.036	1.14	1.25	0.95	0.43	42.45	19.00
L3/T2	2.32	2.70	0.76	0.038	1.14	1.25	0.95	0.43	42.45	16.78
L3/T3	2.84	1.75	0.55	0.054	1.14	1.25	0.95	0.43	42.45	20.91
L3/T4	2.25	1.66	0.61	0.035	1.14	1.25	0.95	0.43	42.45	9.98
L3/T5	1.63	1.81	0.63	0.040	1.14	1.25	0.95	0.43	42.45	16.68
Mean										16.67
L4/T1	1.67	2.06	0.57	0.036	0.79	1.36	0.92	0.36	21.81	2.29
L4/T2	2.32	2.70	0.76	0.038	0.79	1.36	0.92	0.36	21.81	1.28
L4/T3	2.84	1.75	0.55	0.054	0.79	1.36	0.92	0.36	21.81	11.94
L4/T4	2.25	1.66	0.61	0.035	0.79	1.36	0.92	0.36	21.81	5.66
L4/T5	1.63	1.81	0.63	0.040	0.79	1.36	0.92	0.36	21.81	12.01
Mean										6.64
CD										0.40
r	0.18	-0.12	0.24	0.40	0.38	0.01	-0.35	0.20	0.69 ^b	

^a L1 = V20A, L2 = Zs97 A, L3 = IR58025 A, L4 = IR62829 A, T1 = IR24, T2 = IR54742-22-19-3, T3 = IR29723-143-3-2-1, T4 = IR976-19-1, T5 = ARC11353. ^b Significant at 5% level.

Parag 401, a semidwarf rice variety developed through anther culture

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Parag 401 is derived from a cross between Prabhavati and Basmati 370. Anthers coming from the F₁ plants were cultivated to produce doubled haploid plants. Morphology of 70 haplodiploid progenies was studied, and based on yield-related characteristics, selected genotypes were evaluated in multilocation experiments from 1993 to 1996.

Grain quality characteristics of ACR401 compared with selected varieties. Maharashtra, India, 1993-96^a

Character	ACR401 (Parag 401)	Prabhavati	Sugandha	Basmati 370
Plant height (cm)	71.0	75.0	44.0	85.0
Maturity (d)	110	120	116	128
Iron chlorosis reaction	T	T	T	S
Grain yield ^a (t ha ⁻¹)	3.6	3.2	3.3	1.4
Grain type	LS	MS	LS	LS
L/B	4.02	3.20	3.93	4.07
Kernel elongation after cooking	1.53	1.17	1.33	2.00
Gelatinization temperature	I	L	L	I
Protein content(%)	8.30	7.0	8.33	8.40

^a LS = long slender, MS = medium slender, T = tolerant, S = sensitive, L = low, I = intermediate. Av 3 yr.

One of the selections, ACR401 (anther culture rice), showed superior quality characters over the check variety Prabhavati with a similar yield (see table). ACR 401 is resistant to iron chlorosis and has slender grains, high grain length-grain breadth ratio (L/B),

higher kernel elongation after cooking, intermediate amylose content, and scented grains. The genotype ACR 401 has been officially released as Parag 401 for cultivation as an irrigated rice for Vertisols of Maharashtra State. ■